

Data-driven subnational decision-making in the Arctic

Towards Future Actions

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Summary

The recommendations proposed in this policy brief are based on four years of interactions with local and regional decision-makers and other actors in the framework of the Arctic PASSION project. The project focuses on facilitating pan-Arctic data and observation systems and making Arctic data and research more available for users, including increasing their input into decision-making in the region. The ideas in this brief build on three policy briefs produced during the project timeline and have partly been developed and tested with local officials during two workshops in December 2024 and January 2025 (jointly with the Arctic Urban-Regional Cooperation programme) and via interviews. Six broad sets of ideas for actions that were seen as the most feasible and generating the greatest support from engaged decision-makers and researchers have been selected.

1. Research results or outcomes should be usable and easily understandable.

Data producers and researchers should become more familiar with the capacities and limitations of both local policymakers and technical civil servants who use and process the information and data originating from research. The results should be understandable for people without extensive technical and/or natural science background, including local politicians. Findings need to be reported in a concise, effective and targeted manner, including using appropriate visual elements. The presentation of findings should be adjusted to the requirements of policymakers who do not have a background in a given discipline. The methodology should be clearly explained to enhance the trustworthiness of the information. Researchers have to understand better the political context of the decisions that may be taken based on their information.

2. Invest in generating and aggregating data supporting the tracking of social indicators that link directly to climate and environmental strategies.

The socio-economic implications of research findings should be described as much as possible. Research coupled with community engagement or based on co-production may prove more appropriate for generating and monitoring social indicators. Locating findings in a broader socio-economic context may contribute to a greater impact on decision-making.

3. National and EU policymakers should support structured and long-term cooperation between Arctic municipalities and regions regarding climate mitigation/adaptation and economic transitions.

Cooperation frameworks should build on existing initiatives. They should focus on concrete topics and actions rather than only establishing a general framework (e.g., indicators, standards, and benchmarking). Private funding should be considered an option for supporting long-term collaboration between Arctic municipalities and regions.

4. Develop Arctic-specific benchmarks for local actions and policies on green transition and monitor them with accessible tailored tools.

Benchmarks should cover a broad spectrum of issues, including social and socio-economic indicators. They could be developed and operationalised by existing regional and global cooperation initiatives. Identification, collection and promotion of best practices should be a part of any benchmarking framework. Benchmarking should be supported by developing integrated assessment tools for measuring the progress and success of subnational authorities in achieving sustainability goals. However, new benchmarks and monitoring initiatives should avoid putting excessive burdens on municipal civil servants (e.g. extensive reporting).

5. Facilitate the inclusion of data generated at the local level of governance into national and international databases.

Little data generated by or for local authorities is easily accessible to other users. A pan-Arctic database of publicly available impact assessment (EIAs, SEAs) or planning documents could be created. It may also be beneficial to conduct a pilot project with chosen municipalities to include the data they generate in national and international databases.

6. Facilitate long-term collaboration between local decision-makers and local Arctic research institutions.

Good practices of cooperation between municipalities/regions and local research/academic institutions could be collected and promoted. Funding frameworks for research and policy support can serve as enablers of closer cooperation between scientists and municipal officials. Among possible concrete actions are: joint strategies, regular meetings, creating spaces for developing long-term personal relationships between researchers and civil servants, piloting innovative solutions in Arctic municipalities, appointing contact persons for research-local government interactions, as well as involving the private sector in the cooperation.

Recommendation 1:

Research results or outcomes should be provided in a way that is usable and understandable for people without an extensive technical and/or natural science background, including local politicians.

Poor quality of science communication and significant challenges related to the low comprehensibility and applicability of scientific findings are frequently noted by policymakers and other representatives of governance systems - users of such information. Generally, the first recipients of these reports are not politicians but rather specialists/civil servants in specific departments as well as consulting companies contracted by local governments. The difficulties in communicating relevant and comprehensible findings to decision-making processes are not a consequence of the limited literacy levels of policymakers or managers. Rather, they are the result of limited time and resources for interpreting scientific data and knowledge¹.

This problem is particularly acute in the Arctic, where many regional and local authorities - often serving small populations - are constrained by human and financial resources, further limiting their capacity to review numerous data sources and access extensive reports. Stakeholders have identified several characteristics of scientific findings and their presentation that render them "inconvenient" for use. These characteristics include excessive length, extensive technical jargon, ambiguity in methodology and data sources, and impractical conclusions. Such attributes not only diminish the willingness of recipients to engage with the materials but also erode the credibility of the institutions providing them. Consequently, this heightens the need to seek support from consultancy firms that possess the expertise to offer specialised insights and have resources for the translation of scientific information.

"I read a lot of scientific reports, and I often had to read them three or four times to understand what they are talking about because, a lot of times, it is very technical, and you have to look up many terms. If you think about decision-makers, even if it is at a local level, regional level, or national level, they do not have the time or resources to spend to read these reports."

Representative of the North Sweden European Office.

Recommended actions:

Target beneficiary identification: The stakeholders consulted for this project underscored the critical importance of accurately identifying the targeted beneficiaries of scientific materials. To begin, data producers have to be more familiar with the human capacity inherent within specific governance structures. Typically, regional governance bodies have qualified personnel who possess the relevant knowledge and qualifications to interpret scientific materials effectively.

However, in the context of local governance—whether rural or urban—the capacity may be influenced by the size of its administrative staff in relation to the governance responsibilities. Researchers/scientists reporting findings and data should take into account the requirements and limitations of both local politicians and technical civil servants as distinctive target groups (e.g. summary for policymakers needs to be coupled with a short, yet convincing technical background, including an explanation of methodology and the sources of information).

Preferred formats of reporting: In instances where municipalities are small or located in remote areas (such as those in Nunavut, Canada, or Northern Iceland), it is likely that they have limited human and/or financial resources. In these situations, concise executive reports based on data findings are needed. Conversely, larger municipalities such as Tromsø (Norway), Umeå (Sweden), or Rovaniemi (Finland) are more flexible in analysing and reproducing both executive summaries and comprehensive reports. Nevertheless, it remains imperative that these reports include a clearly defined methodology that can be understood and communicated to individuals lacking specialised training.²

Furthermore, raw data sources should be explicitly identified to ensure easy access and retrieval by relevant specialists when questions arise. Data/knowledge producers need to acknowledge that their materials are among multiple sources reviewed by governance structures. Given the substantial workloads of municipal specialists, lengthy reports are often impractical for thorough review. Consequently, preferred formats include executive summaries or infographics/factsheets. Moreover, irrespective of the specific format of any given report, policymakers greatly appreciate findings specifically tailored to a concrete decision-making process. Such an approach ensures that the results are relevant and actionable, thereby facilitating their effective integration into planned initiatives/policy changes/actions.

“When we talk about local decision-makers, we need to be really aware of the facts and figures and where politics enters the picture.”

Representative of the North Norway European Office.

Writing style: In terms of writing style, stakeholders recommend framing scientific materials in a manner that is accessible to individuals without a university education, avoiding overly complex formulas and technical terminology to facilitate quicker comprehension.³ This principle also applies to visual data representations; when faced with extensive technical information, utilising simplified formats, such as colour-coded maps, serves as a more effective means of communication.

The recommended action involves implementing training for scientists and research institutions to effectively translate scientific findings into a language that is more accessible to individuals without specialised backgrounds. Alternatively, the involvement of specialised science communication departments may be necessary to facilitate this translation. Such initiatives aim to enhance public understanding of research outcomes and foster greater engagement with scientific knowledge.

Challenges and opportunities:

The primary risk associated with adhering to the recommendations outlined above lies in the necessity for scientists to adjust their writing and communication styles to those that may be atypical of academic work and more aligned with the practices of private consultancies, which specialise in responding to specific client requests. The scientists consulted reported that, as professionals who primarily engage in academic writing, they encounter difficulties in producing reports that employ plain language, which would be accessible to audiences outside of academia. They raised concerns regarding the potential distortion of factual information when attempting to translate their findings into a language that differs from the conventions of their respective scientific fields.

The arrangement of translation training for scientists and the involvement of specialised science communication departments at research institutions call for considering these institutions' capacity and resources. Governance structures within the Arctic often exhibit a preference for collaborating with private consultancies—such as Asplan Viak (Norway), McKinsey Company (Sweden), McKinley Research Group (USA), and EFLA Company (Iceland) - due to their established reputations for operating on an on-demand basis and their demonstrated adaptability to diverse research methodologies. This preference frequently results in a diminished engagement with local research organisations.

“Simplification is very painful for a scientist, and that is what is going on here. At the same time, there is a lot of power in this type of translation into graphs, maps or tables because it creates an aura of neutrality, objectivity, facts, and truth.

They normally do not. It is just one version of it. I feel a lot around that, the need to simplify absolutely, but to do it transparently. I do this graph and this table, but that also implies creating many invisibilities.”

Representative of the Luleå Technical University.

Furthermore, a significant challenge is the frequent underestimation of the subnational level of governance by scientists. Researchers are often insufficiently informed about the capacity dynamics pertinent to this level, particularly in relation to the Arctic's unique characteristics, such as its sparse population and the stark financial disparities between the northern and southern regions of the Arctic states.

Recommendation 2:

Invest more in generating data and aggregating information related to social indicators linked directly to climate and environmental strategies.

The key responsibility of experts operating in the municipal administrations' sectoral departments is to receive data, analyse it, and explain to policymakers why the data and the issue at hand are significant and actionable. Local policymakers are primarily focused on improving the living standards and quality of life in the communities they serve.

Therefore, their attention typically revolves around the socio-economic conditions of specific communities. During discussions with policymakers from 2021 to 2024, it was highlighted that even larger municipalities, such as Reykjavik, find it challenging to track and plan for changes in human behaviour related to climate change and other management issues. Furthermore, it was noted that a lack of engagement with the community to raise awareness about critical regional and global challenges—like climate change—has contributed to problems such as the overuse of private vehicles, neglect of household waste recycling, and poor dietary habits.

Recommended actions:

Socio-economic implications: Irrespective of the specific nature of research initiatives, projects targeting municipalities or regions should yield results that articulate socio-economic implications related to the proposed measures. This principle should be established as a prerequisite for initiatives that aim to interact with subnational governance structures.

Community engagement: In the context of subnational governance, it is advisable to employ community engagement strategies such as surveys and interviews. These methodologies facilitate the acquisition of not only scientific perspectives on pressing issues, such as climate change, but also societal viewpoints on these matters. A pertinent illustration of such an approach to policymaking can be found in the Reykjavik Climate Action Plan 2021-2025, where the research analysis was combined with community engagement approaches. Engaging with society and incorporating socio-economic factors significantly enhances the relevance and applicability of research. This approach should be regarded as a standard practice within both the policymaking process and policy research.

“The socio-economic aspect is something that’s always asked about in various ways when certain policies are being discussed: what is it going to do to our disadvantaged communities, our marginalised or low-income communities?”

Representative of Sitka Municipal Administration, Alaska.

Climate economy: Consultations conducted during this study have highlighted a significant gap in climate action planning, namely, the necessity of incorporating economic considerations into climate change research. Public administrations are attentive to the potential costs of proposed actions, particularly in relation to the maintenance of infrastructure vulnerable to climate change impacts⁴. Thus, it would be advantageous to integrate economic components into climate change-related analyses and findings provided by researchers into decision-making processes at the local level. Overall, it is recommended that reporting on the targeted subject related to the policymaking process be approached as an in-depth examination of the central issue while deriving conclusions that are relevant across multiple sectors within societal governance.

“I think it is crucial that we have that discussion with our local politicians, and they are also asking for that, especially in the green transition, “What does it cost?” to make a transition, what are the benefits? That is important. Also, looking into specific sectors, like permafrost, how much it will cost to construct on permafrost.”

Representative of Umeå Municipal Administration, Sweden.

Challenges and opportunities:

The primary challenge in the implementation of the recommended actions is linked to the capacities of research institutions and their varying ability to conduct multidisciplinary research covering social indicators of interest for governing structures. In the Arctic context, such research typically necessitates collaboration among multiple research institutions.

Furthermore, the expertise required by policymakers is often absent in many research institutions, particularly in areas such as climate economics and related budgeting software. To undertake this type of research, institutions must not only have adequately trained personnel but also require additional financial resources, which are often limited for Arctic research institutions. Another significant challenge pertains to applying the data and research materials provided. As indicated by policymakers consulted in this study, many issues have political dimensions; thus, decisions may frequently be influenced by political considerations rather than by the empirical evidence presented.

Nonetheless, there are still considerable advantages to analysing socio-economic parameters. Recommended approaches can foster trust between policymakers and research institutions, thereby ensuring policymakers' understanding of the multidisciplinary nature of operating local research institutions and enhancing the practical applicability of research outcomes provided by these institutions.

“Political decisions are political, meaning it is not necessarily factual. So even if we would like all political decisions be evidence-based, knowledge-based as an ideal, this very seldom happens.”

Representative of the North Norway European Office.

Recommendation 3:

National and EU policymakers should consider supporting more structured and long-term cooperation between Arctic municipalities and regions regarding climate mitigation/adaptation and economic transitions.

Policy-makers emphasised the importance of analysing the experiences of other cities, regions, and states in addressing specific challenges. Initiatives aimed at the Arctic local and regional cooperation, including the Arctic Mayors' Forum⁵ and the Arctic Urban-Regional Cooperation Programme (AURC), as well as various efforts extending beyond the Arctic or bringing together larger cities, such as C40⁶ and the initiative for 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030⁷, are designed to assist policy-makers in planning climate actions. These initiatives facilitate dialogue and provide a comparative perspective.

Nevertheless, the added value of such programs lies in the opportunity for municipalities to exchange best practices and explore potential integration into actionable strategies, including with southern municipalities. Nonetheless, many municipalities encounter constraints related to human and financial resources, which limit their capacity to engage in these initiatives effectively.

Recommended actions:

Cost-efficient knowledge and experience exchange:

Currently, municipal and regional cooperation within the Arctic framework is primarily short-term and project-based due to the lack of funding for long-term initiatives, with the exception of the Arctic Mayors' Forum. At the same time, the AURC's example underscores the value of online webinars and policy labs as cost-effective and long-term regular activities aimed at exchanging knowledge and experiences that can be integrated as a platform for intermunicipal dialogue. Learning more about existing funding structures: It is essential to recognise the relevance of existing pan-European or global intermunicipal networks, such as C40⁸ and the Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy⁹, in terms of creating a funding structure for Arctic cooperation.

These cooperation platforms benefit from funding derived from both public and private investments. Given the presence of large-scale enterprises and/or businesses investing in the Arctic region, there exists the potential for collaboration with companies that possess substantial resources to finance intermunicipal cooperation that can be beneficial for both the private sector and local authorities, as establishing enterprises and/or businesses requires not only considerations

of technical capacities, but also discussions about human and social capacities in the areas of the planned operations.

Thematic cooperation: Another recommendation would be to find a topic of mutual interest for knowledge and experience exchange for international funders or international governance and the subnational governance structures in the Arctic. This topic should encompass approaches that are continuously evolving, thereby ensuring their applicability for long-term discussions and the regular production of guiding materials informed by these conversations. For instance, a pertinent subject for consideration is the implementation of international standards for quality management systems (ISOs) within the context of Arctic subnational governance.

Several stakeholders consulted expressed interest in exploring the experiences of other municipalities across the Arctic, particularly in relation to defining the scope of quality management systems and establishing quality objectives that respond to the evolving environmental, technical, and socio-economic conditions of the region (ISO 9001). Moreover, ISO 37120, which addresses sustainable community development and indicators for city services and quality of life, may also be of significant relevance. Although efforts have been 11 made to adapt ISO 37120 to the Arctic context, these initiatives have largely been confined to a limited number of cases¹⁰. Sustained dialogue among various levels of governance in the Arctic has the potential to yield substantial benefits, including the definition of Arctic-specific indicators that accurately monitor progress toward sustainability goals, the identification

of areas needing improvement, and the development of effective strategies¹¹. This initiative aligns with the sustainability objectives outlined in the EU Arctic Policy and may also attract the interest of the European Union as a whole¹².

Promotion: At the same time, the most feasible recommendation would be to promote already established permanent cooperation mechanisms—such as the Arctic Mayors’ Forum (comprising 19 member cities)¹³ and the Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy (which includes 10 Arctic city members)¹⁴. Promotion should involve demonstrating - to prospective members, potential sponsors, and the general public - best practices and the advantages of engaging in or supporting such collaborative efforts. Furthermore, the outreach should extend beyond the Arctic region, as many private funders (including businesses and charitable foundations) may seek to contribute to the development of Arctic dialogue despite having their primary operations located outside of this region.

Challenges and opportunities:

Securing funding for cooperation initiatives that bring together smaller cities and municipalities poses a significant challenge. It is imperative to implement measures that enhance funders’ understanding of the benefits associated with such initiatives while simultaneously exploring alternative and more cost-effective solutions. A key question arises regarding who will be responsible for describing the advantages of knowledge and experience exchange to the funders. Municipalities in the Arctic frequently lack adequate human and financial resources, which complicates their ability to allocate personnel to coordinate promotion and fund-raising campaigns. The same issue persists when considering municipalities’ active involvement in cooperative activities in the case of the successful promotion of already existing initiatives.

Attracting private funding introduces additional complexities. Generally, private funding entails the promotion of funders’ interests and agendas, which may often conflict with the priorities of municipal or regional administrations. This issue is particularly relevant in contexts where, for example, companies operate or intend to operate in Indigenous-populated regions. Even if a private funder agrees to invest in initiatives, there exists a persistent risk of the withdrawal of municipalities who disagree with the funder’s agenda. The primary challenge associated with developing Arctic-specific indicators within international quality management system standards is the limited availability of data in the Arctic region, which is necessary for generating relevant indicators and targets.¹⁵ Nonetheless, including citizens and governance structures in the ongoing and systematic collection of data can partially address this issue.

Given the need to pay attention to stakeholders at the national level (e.g. Governments and/or profile Ministries) as potential drivers of intermunicipal cooperation and dialogue in the Far North, there is often an imbalance of interest in the development of Arctic regions compared to the southern parts of the countries. Local and regional experts involved in consultation processes have observed that national governance bodies, predominantly situated in southern regions, prefer to allocate additional resources to the south rather than to the north.

This preference may be attributed to the fact that the majority of the population resides in southern regions, rendering them more cost-effective targets for resource allocation. The most significant gap in this context pertains to the political influence on decision-making processes. As noted by specialists consulted in this study, while efforts are made to communicate with national governance structures utilising factual information, political motives ultimately drive these decisions.

Effectively implementing the recommendations holds the potential for considerable benefits; through participation in exchange platforms, municipalities can attain comparative insights across regions, learn about best practices in action planning and implementation employed by other cities, and enhance awareness of the challenges faced by subnational entities in the Arctic today.

Recommendation 4:

Develop Arctic-specific benchmarks for local and regional actions and policies on green transition and monitor them with tailored and accessible tools.

There are a number of initiatives providing monitoring frameworks for local governments and communities across the globe with respect to achieving sustainability goals. Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy¹⁶ (GCoM) plays such a role, providing tools and templates for planning, common information and monitoring framework (DATA4CITIES¹⁷ initiative), annual cumulative reporting (for the whole coalition), and awarding communities that excel in different areas of sustainability.

DATA4CITIES aims to provide a standardised approach to measuring progress. Part of members' commitment is to maintain GHG emissions inventories and conduct climate risk and vulnerability assessments. European Arctic cities such as Reykjavik, Akureyri, Tromsø, Bodø, Luleå, Umeå, Boden, Kiruna and Oulu are members of the GCoM coalition.¹⁸ Also, initiatives such as C40¹⁹ and the EU's 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities²⁰ are in place and provide platforms for comparison and benchmarking, although C40 brings together large global cities - and is thus of limited applicability in an Arctic context - and the EU's '100' initiative includes only Reykjavik and Umeå as members located in the northernmost regions. Arctic PASSION interactions with Arctic decision-makers

revealed that the global monitoring and comparison frameworks are not always appropriate for the particular conditions and challenges of Arctic communities. Northern decision-makers may not be able to identify what success means in their specific context if the point of reference is large cities located outside of the Arctic Circle. Arctic-specific benchmarks and indicators could also prove useful in interactions with national governments, allowing presentation of the efforts and achievements of local communities on the pathway to sustainability in an appropriate context.

The advantage of Arctic-specific benchmarks would be the possibility to compare progress with cities that face similar challenges and limitations (remoteness and peripherality, small and sparse populations, long distances, Arctic climate conditions, accelerated climate change, environment recovering more slowly to shocks compared to southern locations, more limited financial and human resources available to Arctic municipalities compared to larger urban centres), rather than comparing themselves with major cities or towns facing very different sets of problems and being able to mobilise significant resources to take actions.

Recommended actions:

What benchmarks? Green transition data and benchmarks can refer to a broad scope of issues, not only carbon emissions, energy efficiency, renewables or public transport, but also socio-economic indicators and signs of behavioural changes, as taken up in previous recommendations.

Who could take it forward? Existing networks such as the Arctic Mayors' Forum²¹ (AMF) and the possible continuation of the Arctic Urban and Regional Cooperation²² (AURC) are possible platforms for developing and operationalising Arctic benchmarks. Exploring Arctic-specific benchmarking and data within the Global Covenant of Mayors' DATA4CITIES initiative could also be explored, perhaps in cooperation with the aforementioned Arctic networks. Another pathway to benchmarking could be through the Arctic Council, which has a history of implementing projects collecting best practices (e.g. renewable energy developments across the Arctic). There is also a space for national actors to take the lead on developing certain tools linked to measuring benchmarks, which could be then used by municipalities across the country and thus aid local governments' interactions with the national level.

Best practices: Showcasing and comparing good practices is a necessary component of any benchmarking framework. There are already initiatives bringing together good practice catalogues, including in the aforementioned GCoM, Arctic Council and the AURC. A more integrated approach to benchmarking and best practice identification and showcasing could make these best practices more visible and impactful.

Integrated assessment tools: Benchmarks and monitoring could be enhanced by tools for assessing policy choices and achievements. A major challenge for municipal and regional green transition planning is the lack of accessible and easy-to-use tools for assessing the impacts of different measures and actions at various levels, from local to global (e.g. linked to resources used, transport and trade). Understanding actions taken at the local level in relation to international value chains and global material/resource use is particularly difficult.²³

Also, accounting for carbon emissions and their changes at the local level remains a challenge. Therefore, there should be an investment in developing new or expanding existing tools supporting (especially smaller) municipalities in assessing their environmental footprint and evaluating the impacts of their actions. Such tools should be easily available, easy to use and designed to minimise the work-effort of municipal civil servants. There are already tools developed by both public and private actors, but they are numerous, often project-based and not integrated.

Moreover, databases for many of these tools are not updated frequently enough (e.g. with respect to the calculation of GHG output of different activities). As consulting companies often play a key role in supporting municipal decision-making in analysis and policy processes, these actors need to be involved in the development of monitoring and assessment tools.

National incentives: Benchmarking cannot be only an exercise for the sake of comparison. In addition to being utilised in local policymaking, it could also play a role in informing national support for local actions, directing funding, and taking account of the specific conditions of Arctic communities within national policies. National governments can, therefore, create incentives for effective benchmarking.

Avoiding new burdens and duplication: New benchmark and monitoring frameworks should not put additional extensive reporting burdens on municipal administrations where capacities are already stretched thin. Arctic benchmarks should be aligned with existing reporting frameworks.

Challenges and opportunities:

Cooperation among local authorities across the globe focused on green transition, has emerged and expanded in response to the failure of actions at global and national levels. Currently, with the USA leaving once more the Paris Agreement and Europe facing economic headwinds and attempting to address structural challenges, there may be new energy in local initiatives aimed at climate, environment and sustainability.

The main challenge for green transition policy benchmarking is the limited human and financial resources available to local actors. There needs to be a clear benefit for local administrations and communities to put resources into benchmarking frameworks. Simultaneously, benchmarking frameworks and assessment tools have to be simple and effective.

On the other hand, however, benchmarking can be seen by decision-makers as a useful instrument in policymaking processes, allowing reconsideration or revisiting of assumptions, creating space for creative thinking about possible actions at the local level, and potentially raising the level of ambition.

Recommendation 5:

Facilitate the inclusion of data generated at the local level of governance into national and international databases.

Local and regional authorities across the Arctic produce a plethora of data covering the state of the Arctic environment, social developments, as well as information obtained through community-based observations and from engagement with Indigenous and traditional knowledge-holders. Much data is collected during the planning processes, environmental (as well as strategic and social) impact assessments (EIAs, SEAs and SIAs) and climate adaptation and mitigation assessment and planning work.

However, most of this information is not included in larger databases or made available to a broader set of data users (researchers, other communities, national decision-makers, and the private sector in general). Often, the information is, in fact, available but has to be requested or is accessible online but hidden on the portals of municipalities or consulting companies. In some places, the data moves through individual data-sharing agreements between parties.

A large part of the information gathered by local authorities stays at the local level without being shared via regional or national databases or services. Accordingly, the rich information produced at the local level during the planning and assessment processes is not available for contribution to national, regional, and international policymaking or to research and global assessment activities. The hope is that adding locally generated data to the pan-Arctic data and monitoring systems would enhance the understanding of changes and processes taking place in the Arctic.

Recommended actions:

A pan-Arctic database of publicly available environmental impact assessment and planning documents. As many EIAs and planning documents are publicly available, a relatively easy first-step option would be to create a platform with links to all such data sources, including information on documents that can be requested from their owners/curators within local administrations.

A pilot action with selected municipalities. The action would entail cooperation with municipalities, consulting companies producing information for municipalities, and national data services. It would explore the best options for including relevant locally produced information in national and international data and observation resources. Easy protocols could be designed and tested, with the focus on limiting the amount of work needed for local civil servants to add the information to databases.

The pilots could have a range of different formats and approaches, e.g. utilising data tools and/or artificial intelligence. Such pilots would test the benefits and added value of “moving the data up from the local level” by reviewing the usefulness of the expanded data availability with the potential users.

Challenges and opportunities:

As for other recommendations in this paper, the limited human and financial capacities of Arctic municipalities present a major challenge to addressing the problem of moving locally produced information to platforms that are more accessible to other potential users. For instance, transferring information to databases may be time-consuming for civil servants while not directly benefiting the municipality or region. Therefore, innovative solutions are necessary.

At the same time, the resources and incentives for this work can be provided by national governments and agencies. Information originating from different processes is produced based on a variety of protocols and may have different formats. Uploading any piece of data produced would require either a significant amount of work or a greater standardisation of processes. National institutions should play a leading role in this respect.

Some of the information produced locally is highly specific to a given process or based on a broader understanding of the environment and human-nature relations. Uploading such information to portals and databases without the context in which it was generated may distort it or make it unusable (this is particularly relevant for information based on Indigenous and/or traditional knowledge). Certain data and information could be accompanied by a degree of explanation of the context in which they were generated.

The above recommended actions would contribute directly to the objectives of the Arctic PASSION project, which is to facilitate an integrated pan-Arctic data and monitoring system of systems where the Arctic data are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR data).

Recommendation 6:

Facilitate long-term collaboration between local decision-makers and local Arctic research institutions.

Local research, academic and learning institutions are important elements of the socio-economic landscape of many municipalities and regions across the circumpolar North. They can also be a valuable and relatively easily available source of expertise to support evidence-based policymaking at local and regional governance levels. Local researchers can also be more anchored within communities, have lived experience of the area and people, and are less likely to engage in fly-in-fly-out research practices.

There appears to be a benefit to cultivating direct, long-lasting personal relationships between Arctic researchers and Arctic officials and civil servants. Ideally, such relationships can also play a role in enhancing community engagement and, in some cases, the inclusion of Indigenous and/or traditional knowledge into decision-making.

There are many different practices and approaches to such cooperation, ranging from structured, formal cooperation agreements to personal interactions between particular researchers and decision-makers. The latter often prove especially effective and impactful. There are many good examples where regional and university authorities attempt to align their strategies (e.g. Nord University and Nordland County in North Norway). Some municipalities make use of services provided by local colleges and research institutes, e.g. with respect to environmental impact assessment.

There are attempts to involve academia in regional economic clusters (e.g. Lapland's smart specialisation strategy or innovation alliance between the City of Oulu and the University of Oulu in Finland). However, in other locations, civil servants appear to have no interactions with local academic institutions. Some agreements between universities and municipalities remain at a declaratory level and do not generate concrete results or inputs. The key challenge is finding appropriate experts on both sides and bringing them together. There are usually major differences between specific policy issues and scientific disciplines - in some cases, cooperation is easier and often smooth, while in others non-existent.

"There are quite many challenges [for cooperation between municipalities and universities]. It's always difficult to find right people right experts from both sides"

Representative of the City of Oulu administration, Finland

Recommended actions:

At the Arctic level, collecting good practices of cooperation between municipalities and regions and local research and academic institutions. As there is a wide spectrum of formats and practices, it would be beneficial to review these approaches and highlight those that could be inspirational to decision-makers, researchers and academic institutions across the Arctic. That could be led by the University of the Arctic, Arctic Mayors' Forum, or Arctic Six (A6) cooperation.²⁴

At the local level, implementing specific actions, including:

- encouraging regular meetings between the university and municipal/regional staff with respect to strategic alignment and regularly reviewing activities (e.g. in the form of joint workshops) to find areas of common concern or alignment;
- adopting joint strategies;
- formal cooperation agreements focused on practical actions;
- identifying concrete areas and specific formats for cooperation and concrete actions to avoid agreements remaining at a superficial, general level;
- piloting innovative solutions in Arctic municipalities;
- establishing contact points for decision-makers at the universities (and/or through networks such as A6) to help identify needed expertise and contacts;
- appointing contact persons within municipalities and regions with the responsibility to engage with research institutions;
- creating spaces and incentives for direct (personal) interactions and relations between researchers and civil servants (also for both sides to learn what they are actually doing);
- organising (possibly pan-Arctic) training for researchers on the modalities of engagement with local and regional decision-makers;
- locally-based researchers could be more often engaged as translators of available data in the context of specific decision-making/planning processes or programmes implemented at the local level (a function that is often performed by consulting companies);
- involving the private sector in the cooperation between researchers and decision-makers.

Adjusting funding frameworks for research and policy support (by local governments but also by national and EU funding agencies) that enable researchers to contribute to local decision-making directly.

Challenges and opportunities:

The research and learning institutions located in Arctic communities are often relatively small and may focus on disciplines that are not necessarily directly useful for municipal/regional evidence-based decision-making. In such cases, it would be important to find ways to identify benefits and modes of cooperation. Moreover, local researchers can also serve as bridges to expertise located elsewhere (i.e., in the south of the Arctic countries or abroad).

Civil servants often need very concrete inputs and researchers are not able to provide information at the required level of specificity and practicality. That is a broader problem for the science-policy nexus, which may, however, also be seen as an opportunity for Arctic researchers: cooperation with municipalities can support identifying the societal benefits of their own research, which could be a key for attracting funding and facilitating societal support for science. On the other hand, local decision-makers need to understand the limits of research institutions' capabilities - what they can do and what they cannot deliver.

Another challenge is the Western mindset of some researchers - even those employed in local institutions - who work in areas inhabited by Indigenous Peoples. Scientists may not be attentive to or familiar enough with Indigenous knowledge systems, which adversely impacts their capability to interact with Arctic

communities and contribute to local governance. Civil servants and officials usually have very limited time to search for information and investigate whether someone at a local university conducts relevant research. Conversely, in some Arctic municipalities and regions, there is a degree of flow of experts between local government and research institutions, which contributes to cooperation.

There is a risk that agreements between universities and regions/municipalities are general and vague and do not provide concrete results. Often, such agreements need to be treated only as starting frameworks, while concretisation of the cooperation requires effort and long-term commitment from both sides. Finding specific areas of focus for cooperation - such as digitalisation or health - may be important foundations for operationalising the cooperation.

The establishment of the A6 (earlier A5) network of Nordic Arctic universities creates opportunities for stronger engagement and exchange of best practices. There appears to be a degree of interest among A6 member institutions and local Arctic decision-makers to enhance cooperation. Moreover, the University of the Arctic and its thematic networks could be used to a greater extent as a platform for facilitating practices of academic-local governance cooperation.

Methodology

Beginning in the latter half of 2021, the University of Lapland team undertook a series of consultations with a diverse array of stakeholders, including policymakers and managers from relevant Arctic national, regional, and local administrations and scientists engaged in research relevant to Arctic decision-making.²⁵ The focus of these interactions was to explore the integration of research and science-based knowledge into policymaking processes. The process was conducted through semi-structured in-depth interviews and a number of workshops.

Stakeholders were approached using previously established contacts in municipalities across the Arctic, along with direct requests for interviews.²⁶ The Arctic PASSION online workshop was held in June 2022, and an in-person workshop titled “Science and Evidence-Based Policymaking: Towards New Steps with the Arctic PASSION Project and Arctic Mayors’ Forum” was organised by the University of Lapland in collaboration with the Arctic Mayors’ Forum at the Rovaniemi Arctic Spirit Conference in November 2023. Furthermore, the process included two Policy Labs with policymakers: 1) at the Arctic Futures Symposium 2024 in Brussels, Belgium (in-person), as well as 2) an online Policy Lab with partners from the Arctic Urban Regional Cooperation Programme, organised in January 2025. Findings from this process were successively synthesised in Deliverables 7.2, 7.4, and 7.6.

Based on these inputs, the University of Lapland team identified a broad array of policy ideas and selected six recurring topics of concern expressed by stakeholders as a basis for the development of recommendations. By synthesising the inputs from the four years of interacting with policymakers and other stakeholders, supported by secondary research, the team developed recommendations in the form of the current Policy Brief for future research initiatives aimed at fostering collaboration with Arctic subnational governance structures.

Endnotes

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24. Cooperation between six universities in Northern Fennoscandia. Arctic Six. Available at <https://www.arcticsix.org/>
25. List of Arctic states, regions, municipalities and institutions consulted can be found in the University of Lapland produced Deliverables 7.2 (available at <https://zenodo.org/records/13320739>), 7.4 (available at <https://zenodo.org/records/8055176>) and 7.6 (available at <https://zenodo.org/records/11242175>)
26. Detailed methodology of interactions with key stakeholders described in Deliverable 7.2, 7.4 and 7.6.

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